

Potentiometric Determination of Hydrazine or Lead Tetra acetate

M. R. MAHMOUD, M. S. EL-MELIGY and I. M. ISSA*

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt, A. R. E.

Manuscript received 1 February 1977, revised 20 May 1977, accepted 24 May 1977

Hydrazine is oxidized quantitatively in acid solutions with lead IV acetate to yield nitrogen by the loss of 4-electrons. The factors affecting the success of potentiometric determination of hydrazine with lead IV acetate are investigated. As little as 0.13 mg of N_2H_4 per .0 ml of solution can be determined accurately in presence of 0.87M acetic acid. The reserve titration of lead IV acetate with N_2H_4 can be applied for the determination of lead tetraacetate. The reaction proceeds quantitatively within the concentration range 0.202-2.02 mg of Pb per 50 ml of solution. The titrations at the optimum conditions proceed fast and with adequate accuracy. The equivalent point in both cases is marked by a large potential jump.

LEAD IV acetate has been recently applied as an analytical reagent for the determination of many reducing agents including As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mo^{3+} , Ti^{1+} and Ru^{4+} .¹ The oxidation of N_2H_4 with Pb IV acetate has not been investigated, although different oxidizing agents have been applied for the determination of hydrazine depending upon its oxidation to nitrogen and water²⁻⁷. Recently Issa *et al.*⁸ developed a method for the determination of N_2H_4 as low as 0.32 mg using potassium permanganate as oxidizing agent in presence of fluoride ions.

The present study deals with the reaction between Pb IV acetate and Hydrazine in order to devise a method for the determination of macro- and micro-amounts of hydrazine or lead IV acetate.

Experimental

a) Chemicals and Solutions :

Lead IV acetate : The solid was prepared according to Braner⁹ by heating Pb_3O_4 with a mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride at 60°. The product was purified by recrystallization from acetic acid. ~0.05 M solution was then prepared by dissolving the appropriate weight of the solid in glacial acetic acid. The solution was then standardized potentiometrically against standard Fe II sulphate solution¹⁰.

Hydrazine sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving the A.R. product in redistilled water. The reducing power of hydrazine was determined by recommended procedure¹¹. Dilute solutions of hydrazine sulphate and lead IV acetate were prepared by quantitative successive dilution.

Other reagents were of analytical grade, twice distilled water and glacial acetic acid were used for the preparation of solutions and titration media.

b) Equipment :

The e.m.f. of the titration cell was measured by a direct reading millivoltmeter using a saturated calomel electrode as reference half-cell. A platinum electrode was used as indicator electrode which was always abraded with emery paper, etched with aqua regia and rinsed with water or glacial acetic acid before being used in each titration according to the medium in which the titration is performed.

On using hydrazine as titrant, the reference half-cell was connected to the titration cell with potassium chloride and Na-Ac acetic acid salt bridges.

c) Working procedure :

In the direct method appropriate volumes of solutions containing amounts of N_2H_4 ranging between 0.13-13.12 mg mixed with acetic acid to give an acidity of 0.174-8.70 M are titrated with lead IV acetate. In the reverse process different volumes of lead IV acetate containing 0.202-2.02 mg Pb in presence of acetic acid concentration > 6.96 M are titrated with N_2H_4 . The sudden change in the potential in both cases indicate the end point.

Results and Discussion

A) Titration of Hydrazine by Lead Tetra Acetate :

Effect of acetic acid concentration : Table 1, shows that good end points are obtained at acidities ranging between 0.174-8.70 M acetic acid. The titration curves obtained are more or less smooth and characterized by sharp inflections at the end points. The values of the formal redox potential of the N_2/N_2H_4 system depicted from the titration curves, indicate that the values shift slightly to more positive potential on increasing the acidities and hence hydrogen ions must be involved in the reaction of hydrazine with lead tetra acetate.

Acidity, M CH_3COOH 0.174, 0.348, 0.87, 1.74, 3.48, 5.22, 8.70
Redox potential of N_2/N_2H_4 couple, 0.310, 0.320, 0.33, 0.34, 0.35, 0.355, 0.365 Volt, Vs S.C.E.

*Deceased December, 1977

TABLE 1—TITRATION OF 5ml 0.082 N N₂H₄ WITH 0.0972 N Pb(AC)₄ IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT AMOUNTS OF ACETIC ACID.

N ₂ acetic acid	Theoretical end point, (ml)	Experimental end point, (ml)	Error %	Inflection at end point, mV/0.05 ml titrant
0.174	4.21	4.23	+0.12	280
0.348	4.21	4.22	+0.23	290
0.870	4.21	4.24	+0.71	270
1.74	4.21	4.24	+0.71	270
3.48	4.21	4.23	+0.47	290
5.22	4.21	4.24	+0.71	300
8.70	4.21	4.21	nil	240

Effect of hydrazine concentration: Amounts of hydrazine ranging between 0.13-13.12 mg can be determined with errors not exceeding 0.70%, on using the proper concentration of acetic acid (Table, 2.) The titration curves possess almost the same character irrespective of the concentration of N₂H₄ and are characterized by sharp inflections at the end point, which amount to 120-140 mV/0.05 ml of Pb IV acetate in dilute solutions. With larger amounts of hydrazine the end points are attained earlier than those expected, a fact which is readily attributed to the partial production of N₂H₂.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OBTAINED FOR THE POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF HYDRAZINE WITH Pb IV ACETATE.

ml, mg of N ₂ H ₄ , N ₂ H ₄	Theoretical end point ml	Experimental end point ml	Error %	Inflection at end point, mV/0.05 ml of titrant
Titration of 0.082 N N ₂ H ₄ with 0.0976 N Pb(AC) ₄				
2	1.30	1.685	+0.72	250
5	3.28	4.21	+0.24	290
10	6.56	8.42	+0.23	300
15	9.84	12.63	+0.08	320
20	13.12	16.84	-0.35	325
25	16.40	21.10	-1.32	325
45	29.32	37.89	-2.40	380
Titration of 0.0082 N N ₂ H ₄ with 0.00976 N Pb(AC) ₄				
2	0.13	1.685	-0.29	120
5	0.328	4.21	+0.24	130
10	0.656	8.42	-0.44	140

B) Titration of lead IV acetate with hydrazine :

Effect of acetic acid concentration: The data in Table 3 represent the titration of PbIV acetate with hydrazine at different acetic acid concentrations. The results indicate that the volume of hydrazine solution consumed in the titration is concordant with the theoretical one, corresponding to the oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen and reduction of Pb⁴⁺ to Pb²⁺. It is worthy to mention that the acetic acid concentration should exceed 6.96 M, otherwise Pb⁴⁺ may undergo hydrolysis to yield PbO₂. The titration curves are

smooth and characterized by sharp inflections at the end point amounting on the average to 345-380 mV/0.05 ml of N₂H₄.

TABLE 3—TITRATION OF 5ml 0.0976 N Pb(AC)₄ WITH 0.082 N N₂H₄ IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT AMOUNTS OF ACETIC ACID.

Total normality	Theoretical end point (ml)	Experimental end point (ml)	Error (%)	Inflection at end point mV/0.05 ml of titrant
6.96	5.95	5.98	+0.50	360
8.70	5.95	5.98	+0.50	355
10.44	5.95	5.98	+0.50	345
13.90	5.95	6.00	+0.84	380

Effect of lead tetra acetate concentration: As is evident from the data included in Table 4, the titration of Pb IV acetate with N₂H₄ can be used as an analytical method for the determination of amounts as small as 0.202 mg of Pb IV. The titration curves are characterized by sharp inflection at the end point amounting to 50) mV/0.05 ml of N₂H₄.

TABLE 4—RESULTS OBTAINED FOR THE POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF Pb IV ACETATE WITH HYDRAZINE.

ml of Pb(AC) ₄	mg of Pb(AC) ₄	mg of Pb	Theoretical end point (ml)	Experimental end point (ml)	Error (%)	Inflection at end point, mV/0.05ml of titrant
Titration of 0.0976 Pb IV acetate with 0.082 N N ₂ H ₄						
2	43.40	20.20	2.38	2.40	+0.84	420
5	108.50	50.50	5.95	6.00	+0.84	430
10	217.00	101.00	11.90	12.00	+0.84	440
20	434.00	202.00	23.80	23.90	+0.42	490
30	651.00	303.00	35.82	36.85	+2.87	580
Titration of 0.00976 N Pb(AC) ₄ with 0.0082 N N ₂ H ₄						
2	4.34	2.02	2.38	2.38	Nil	220
6	13.02	6.06	7.14	7.08	-0.84	240
Titration of 0.000976 N Pb(AC) ₄ with 0.00082 N N ₂ H ₄						
2	0.434	0.202	2.38	2.36	-0.84	120
5	1.085	0.505	5.95	5.96	-0.16	140

From the quantities reacting at equivalence point at the optimum conditions, it is concluded that hydrazine is oxidized with PbIV acetate to nitrogen, where the reaction takes place can be considered to proceed according to the following equation :

This reaction is based on the two partial reactions :

From the results obtained, it is deduced that the oxidation of N_2H_4 with lead IV acetate is a quantitative reaction. This is supported by calculating the equilibrium constant and the degree of completion of the reaction. These are found to amount $6.92 \times 10^{18.0}$ and $3.47 \times 10^{2.2}$ respectively. These values were calculated from the potential of the systems involved viz.

$$E^{\circ}_{\text{Pb IV/Pb II}} = 1.70 \text{ V} \text{ and } E^{\circ}_{\text{N}_2/\text{N}_2\text{H}_4} = -0.23 \text{ V.}$$

However, on using the formal potential values, depicted from the titration curves, K and α are found to amount to $3.55 \times 10^{4.8}$ and 1.18×10^3 respectively.

In addition, the method under hand involve an easy and accurate method for the micro- and macro-determination of Pb IV acetate where a few methods are known for this purpose^{10,14}.

References

1. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "New Redox Titrants", Pergamon Press, London, 1st Edition, 1956, p. 79.

2. G. S. JAMIESON, *Am. J. So.*, 1912, 33, 352.
 3. A. KURTENACKER and J. WAGNER, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1922, 120, 261.
 4. E. J. CAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1810.
 5. A. BENRATH and K. RULAND, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1920, 11L, 267.
 6. I. M. ISSA and R. M. ISSA, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1956, 14, 573.
 7. G. R. GOPALA and P. V. R. KRISHNA, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1973, 65, 347.
 8. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA, A. M. HAMMAM and M. R. MAHMOUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, LIII, 698.
 9. C. BRANER, "Hand Buch der preparative an organischen chemie" Stuttgart 1960, Band I.
 10. A. BERKA, V. DVORAK, I. NEMEC and J. ZYKA, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1960, 23, 380.
 11. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" Longman, Green Company, Co., London, 1959, p. 365.
 12. A. BERKA, V. DVORAK, I. NEMEC and J. ZYKA, *J. Electro-analyt. Chem.*, 1962, 4, 150.
 13. K. A. IDRIS, I. M. ISSA and M. S. EL-MELIGY, *Indian J. of Chem.*, 1976, 14A(3), 195.